

ISSUES OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN COMBATING MONEY LAUNDERING

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Annotation: This article describes the procedure for organizing cooperation with competent authorities of foreign countries in investigating the legalization of proceeds from criminal activities during the implementation of judicial and legal reforms, its specific aspects, and procedural significance. The article examines the scope of application of this cooperative framework through the views put forward by scholars on organizing collaboration with competent authorities of foreign countries in investigating the legalization of proceeds from criminal activities. Based on the perspectives and ideas proposed by scholars, the issue of "organizing cooperation with competent authorities of foreign countries in investigating the legalization of proceeds from criminal activities" was analyzed through scientific, theoretical, practical, and legislative norms.

Key words: criminal case, legalization, cooperation, proceeds from criminal activity, authorized bodies, money laundering

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается процедура организации сотрудничества с компетентными органами зарубежных стран в расследовании легализации доходов от преступной деятельности в контексте проведения судебно-правовых реформ, ее специфические аспекты и процессуальное значение. В статье рассматривается сфера применения данной формы сотрудничества через призму взглядов ученых на организацию взаимодействия с компетентными органами зарубежных стран при расследовании случаев легализации доходов от преступной деятельности. На основе представленных учеными перспектив и идей вопрос "организации сотрудничества с компетентными органами зарубежных стран в расследовании случаев легализации доходов, полученных от преступной деятельности" был проанализирован с точки зрения научных, теоретических и практических аспектов, а также законодательных норм.

Ключевые слова: уголовное дело, легализация, сотрудничество, доходы от преступной деятельности, уполномоченные органы, отмывание денег.

In the context of globalization, cases of individuals who have committed crimes exporting and concealing proceeds from criminal activities in foreign countries are becoming increasingly widespread. This necessitates the establishment of mutual cooperation between states in the field of recovering such income, particularly the regulation of these issues in national legislation.

The UN Convention against Corruption (Section 5) and the Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (Article 14) stipulate the obligation of member states to take measures to recover proceeds from criminal activity.

At present, the absence of a mechanism for seizing and confiscating property obtained from criminal activity in the criminal procedural legislation of Uzbekistan is creating difficulties in establishing international cooperation in this area. For this reason, it is important to study this issue from a scientific and theoretical perspective.

Currently, the problem of international search, seizure, and confiscation of money and property obtained through criminal means has become a matter of special attention from international bodies and organizations. In particular, the United Nations and its sponsored organizations are paying constant attention to the development of specific mechanisms for providing international legal assistance in the investigation of crimes, including in the search for, arrest and confiscation of income derived from criminal activity. In recent years, there has been a trend towards a more in-depth study of the issues of supplementing recommendatory norms with specific content, searching for, seizing, and confiscating income from criminal activity from the perspective of practical needs.

Examples include the UN Convention on Combating Illicit Trafficking in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances of December 20, 1988, the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime of November 15, 2000, the International Convention on Combating the Financing of Terrorism of December 9, 1999, the recommendations of the Special Financial Action Task Force on Money Laundering (FATF), and the CIS Model Law "On Combating Money Laundering" of December 8, 1998.

The experience of some foreign countries in this area has been studied. In particular, according to Article 577 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, on the basis of a request (assignment, petition) for legal

assistance, the competent authorities of the Republic of Kazakhstan carry out procedural actions provided for by this Code in order to identify and seize property, money and valuables obtained by criminal means, as well as property belonging to suspects, accused or convicted persons. In addition, these requested properties should be used as evidence in a criminal case. Also, in the order of recognition and enforcement of the court decision of a foreign state, the issue of confiscation of income from criminal activity may be considered.

When studying the practice of the United Kingdom on the issue of seizure and confiscation at international request, this issue is regulated by the Proceeds of Crime Act 2002, POCA, which states that in the United Kingdom, seizure of property at the request of foreign states can be carried out in the following cases:

- Property related to criminal activities such as corruption, money laundering, tax evasion, terrorism, or other transnational crimes.
- Property can be used to compensate for damage caused to victims or to pay fines.
- If there is a suspicion that the property was purchased at the expense of income obtained illegally.

The UK has strong legal instruments to seize property at the request of foreign countries. Through mechanisms such as the Proceeds from Crime Act and the Inexplicable Wealth Orders, the country is effectively fighting money laundering and protecting international interests. At the same time, the UK ensures that decisions can be appealed to the courts, while respecting the rights of owners.

When studying the experience of the Russian Federation, this area is regulated by the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation and the Federal Law "On Combating Money Laundering." According to it, confiscated property can be transferred to a foreign state if it is provided for in an international agreement. Also, these assets can be obtained from criminal activity and, if a request is received, can be seized by a court decision and sent at the request of a foreign state.

The Bulgarian Criminal Procedure Code also contains a norm analogous to the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The proposed additions are made in order to eliminate the legal gap in this area and regulate the issues of search, seizure, confiscation of property obtained from criminal activity in national legislation. Recently, experts have been

thoroughly analyzing the compliance of the legislation of Uzbekistan related to the confiscation and return of assets with international standards.

Specifically, as a state party to the UN Convention against Corruption, it is obliged to organize measures to return proceeds from corruption crimes under Article 31.[2]

Conclusions

Having studied the above, it is proposed to supplement the Criminal Procedure Code with Article 592-2 titled "Reflux of Income Obtained from Criminal Activity from a Foreign State."

The bodies of inquiry, investigation, courts and execution shall carry out the procedural actions provided for by this Code in accordance with the legislation and international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the detection and seizure of income received from criminal activity and exported outside the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

If there is a need to send a request for the execution of procedural actions for the identification, arrest, confiscation and return of income obtained from criminal activity and exported outside the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all necessary materials are submitted to the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan to resolve the issue of sending this request.

The request of the investigative and inquiry body to send a request to the competent authority of a foreign state to perform procedural actions and all documents attached to it shall be considered by the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan - in accordance with the international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan or on the basis of the principle of reciprocity, sends a request in the manner prescribed by the Criminal Procedure Code on the execution of procedural actions for the identification, arrest, confiscation and return of income from criminal activity, as well as property belonging to the suspect, accused, defendant or convicted person. Such a request shall be signed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan or his deputy.

References:

1. Немцов Ю.И., Аржанова И.М.. Построение системы возврата активов в зарубежных государствах (на примере стран ЕС) / Экономическая и финансовая безопасность. 1/2017. ст. 56-63.;
2. Конвенция Организации Объединенных Наций против коррупции, принята резолюцией Ген. Асс. ООН 58/4 от 31.10.2003 года;

3. Forsaith J., Irving B., Nanopoulos E., Fazekas M. Study for an Impact Assessment on a Proposal for a New Legal Framework on the Confiscation and Recovery of Criminal Assets. DRR-5380-EC. Final Report Prepared for the European Commission Directorate General Home Affairs Published 2012 by the RAND Corporation//http://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/doc_centre/crime/docs/RAND%20EUROPE%20Study%20Final%20Report.pdf //;
4. <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2018C00090>//Federal Register of Legislation.Proceeds of Crime Act 2002.

